

Literature & case study review on outcomes in payments for ecosystem services / compensation for ecosystem services (PES/CES) programmes

Case study questionnaire: Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES)

The goal of the case studies is to illuminate the overarching questions: How are values articulated through PES programs, and how do these shape social and environmental outcomes?

How do decision-makers make 'trade-offs' among multiple values, and whose values come to matter, and how? To address these questions each case study will examine, based on the available literature, the process from PES design and implementation through documented outcomes, with attention to how diverse values were articulated by various actors throughout the process; how they came to influence (or not) program design, implementation, or outcomes; and how this was shaped by relevant institutions (including those established by PES programs and pre-existing or parallel ones) to influence social and environmental outcomes. We're particularly concerned with identifying (mis)alignments between upstream participants' values and program design, and 'participants' refers to upstream participants in the questions below.

This document lays out the questions we aim to address for each case study, recognizing that gaps in the literature will exist for all cases and that this approach will help to identify those gaps. Each case study should address each of the numbered topics (1-5) in a few paragraphs each, aiming to cover as many of the sub-questions (a, b, c, etc.) as possible and identifying evidence gaps as appropriate. After submission for the case studies, the analysis will involve reading across the cases to examine processes of value articulation throughout program design and implementation and how they translate into outcomes, e.g. through negotiation, conflict, and trade-offs. The analysis will attend to multiple dimensions of justice throughout the process (as described in the section outline). The goal is not to be comparative, but to identify tendencies in terms of e.g. successful value articulation strategies, and how power relations influence program design and trade-offs throughout.

- 1) **Background and context:** *This topic gives an introduction to the program and briefly outlines the contextual factors most relevant to the case study. Recognizing that this cannot be comprehensive, this is a space to outline the necessary background information that may be essential to understanding*

the case. These factors may also be brought up later in response to specific questions. Factors to consider include:

- a) Brief description of the program (for introductory purposes):
 - i) Geographical extent, ecosystem services (ES) rewarded, approximate level of participation, type of compensation.
 - ii) Relevant global standards/programs/certifications (e.g. REDD+, carbon or ecosystem service certifications)
 - b) Contextual factors:
 - i) Biophysical conditions
 - ii) Socio-economic conditions
 - (1) Land tenure
 - (2) Land inequities
 - (3) Structural inequalities and legacies of colonization, disenfranchisement, etc.
 - iii) Political conditions
 - (1) Governance context (relevant institutional framework and policy context, including related policy and legislation)
 - iv) Power relations and political influence among stakeholders
- 2) **Problematization and framing (defining the problem):** *This topic aims to cover the process of defining the environmental problem that the PES program was intended to address. We want to identify how the program was initially designed, while the following topic on Value Articulation will provide the opportunity to describe how this changed over time. We recognize that there may be research gaps in these early stages for many programs.*
- a) How was the environmental problem defined? Who was empowered in/excluded from this decision?
 - b) How was PES chosen as the solution? Who was empowered in/excluded from this decision?
 - c) What ecosystem services (ES) were prioritized in the initial design? Who was identified as beneficiaries and potential providers of ES, and how?

3) **Values and value articulation:** *This topic digs more deeply into how values are articulated by various actors throughout the process of PES design and implementation, through environmental valuation methods like multi-criteria analysis (MCA), spatial targeting or ecosystem modeling, or political strategies like referenda, petitions, or protest or sabotage, and what kinds of values were articulated through these processes. We aim to cast a wide net to include strategies that were included in program design as well as those used by actors to contest design or implementation later on. The range of methods/strategies that are relevant here will depend on the case.*

- a) What value articulation method(s) was/were used in the initial design process (e.g. MCA, ecosystem modeling/targeting, referenda, focus groups, etc.)? How was spatial targeting and prioritization done? How were upstream participants/ES 'providers' targeted?
 - i) How and by whom were these methods chosen?
 - ii) Who was involved? What roles did they play?
- b) How and why did some values become influential over others in program design and/or implementation?
 - i) What values were reflected/excluded in the design process? What forms of knowledge? What worldviews?
 - ii) Whose values were reflected/excluded? Whose knowledge? Whose worldviews?
 - iii) Was this process contested? If so how? (E.g. other strategies by which marginalized values might be expressed – protest, counter-organizing, sabotage).
- c) Were trade-offs made among multiple objectives, and if so how and by whom?

4) Distribution of costs and benefits:

- a) Benefits:
 - i) Compensation/payments:
 - (1) What kind of compensation is used (in-kind vs. monetary)?
 - (2) How and to whom are benefits distributed (e.g. individual landholders/households, community organizations, etc.)? Based on what criteria (equity, need, etc.)?

- (3) How were distribution decisions made (who was involved, what was the nature of their participation)? This may reference material above.
- (4) Do participants perceive distribution and compensation as just? Why or why not? Were distribution decisions contested, and if so how?
- (5) What do participants perceive as benefits of the program (i.e. other motivations that might not be represented in compensation; this may include ecological benefits)?

b) Distribution of costs

- i) Whose conduct is impacted by the program? Whose conduct is defined as problematic?
- ii) What land-use or other changes were required of participants? How are these changes enforced (conditionality)?
- iii) How are the costs of participation measured/accounted for (e.g. monetary opportunity costs, social and cultural impacts of livelihood change, etc.)?
- iv) What did participants perceive as costs of participation (might show mismatch between compensation and motivations)?

5) **Outcomes:** *This topic examines what has been documented in program monitoring and relevant literature on social and ecological outcomes. The volume of evidence available for each case will vary considerably, and there will likely be discrepancies between outcomes at different scales (e.g. local project-level outcomes vs. national program outcomes).*

a) Social outcomes (based on program monitoring, where available, and subsequent studies)

- i) Does the program have specific social impact goals? Is there monitoring for these, and how?
- ii) What social impacts have been documented (through program monitoring and in wider literature)?
 - (1) What methods/proxies were used, and at what spatial and temporal scales?
 - (2) What was the direction or magnitude of change?
- iii) What are participants' perceptions of the program's social impacts?

b) Ecological impacts (based on program monitoring, where available, and subsequent studies)

- i) What ecological outcomes are prioritized, for what beneficiaries, and how are these monitored?
 - ii) What changes in ES or other impacts have been documented (in program monitoring and wider literature)? What monitoring protocols were implemented?
 - (1) What methods/proxies were used, and at what spatial and temporal scales?
 - iii) How do upstream participants and/or downstream stakeholders perceive ecological impacts? (Might show disconnect between ES monitored and impacts of interest to participants or other stakeholders).
- c) Participation:
- i) (How) have participation levels and longevity been assessed? What is the extent of participation in the areas covered by the program?
 - ii) What evidence exists in the literature regarding the main factors influencing participation (e.g. non-monetary motivations, barriers, availability of alternative labor markets or livelihood options, etc.)? This may overlap with material above.
- d) Other outcomes and research gaps
- i) Effects on land tenure?
 - ii) Off-site impacts/leakage?
 - (1) Is there evidence of off-site or indirect social or environmental impacts, including e.g. impacts on other labor markets, social cohesion, cultural practices, or broader environmental impacts due to intensification of agriculture or land conversion elsewhere?
 - iii) Is there evidence of 'value crowding,' positive or negative?